

Outdoor Learning in the Australian Curriculum

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Four walls, a roof and a door. For some teachers, this is all that stands between the controlled world of education and the unknown world of Outdoor Learning.

In this article, I hope to highlight the incredible learning opportunities that are present by using the outdoors as a teaching tool embedded within any curricula in the Victorian Curriculum Learning Areas.

Outdoor Learning means different things to different people, depending on their location, background or relationship to positive or negative outdoor experiences. For this article, we will refer to The Australian Curriculum's definition:

Outdoor learning engages students in practical and active learning experiences in natural environments and settings, and this typically takes place beyond the school classroom. In these environments, students develop the skills and understandings to move safely and competently while valuing a positive relationship with natural environments and promoting the sustainable use of these environments.¹

Australia has a long connection with the outdoors dating back thousands of years with Australia's Indigenous inhabitants, however, according to Lugg (2004)² and

1 Australian Curriculum. (n.d.). Outdoor Learning. Retrieved 11/10/2020 from <https://www.australiancurriculum.edu.au/resources/curriculum-connections/portfolios/outdoor-learning/>

2 Lugg, A., (2004) 'Outdoor adventure in Australian outdoor education: Is it a case of roast for Christmas dinner?' *Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education*, 8(1), pp. 4–11.

Brookes (2002)³ Australian programs have generally been shaped by northern hemisphere and UK traditions.

Outdoor Learning does not exist as a standalone curriculum concept and is introduced as one of four curriculum connections by the Australian Curriculum that include 'Consumer and financial literacy, Food and Fibre, Food and wellbeing, Multimedia, Online safety and Outdoor learning'. These curriculum connections allow educators in all learning areas to draw connections across the dimensions of Australian Curriculum and provide pathways to search, access, and organise content through Foundation to Year 10 (Australian Curriculum, n.d.).⁴

Why Is Outdoor Learning Important?

Growing up in Australia, 2018⁵ found that "One generation ago 73% of Children's playtime was spent outdoors" whereas "now 13% of children's total playtime is spent outdoors". "In the new millennium, only 1 in 5 children have ever climbed a tree, an experience enjoyed by two-thirds of their parents." (*Growing up in Australia*, 2018).

3 Brookes, A., (2002) 'Lost in the Australian bush: Outdoor education as curriculum'. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 34(4), pp. 405–425.

4 Australian Curriculum. (n.d.). *Curriculum connections*. Retrieved 11/10/2020 from <https://www.australiancurriculum.edu.au/resources/curriculum-connections/>

5 *Growing up in Australia*. (2018) *Annual statistical reports 2018*. Retrieved 11/10/2020 from <https://growingupinaustralia.gov.au/research-findings/annual-statistical-reports-2018>

Figure 1: Learning in the outdoors

This is just one of the numerous research articles including the 2018 Report card by Active Healthy Kids,⁶ Copeland, Khoury and Kalkwarf (2016)⁷ and Taylor et al (2009)⁸ that highlight that Australian young people are spending less time outdoors in comparison to previous generations and the flow on effects that this has throughout their educational journey.

The benefits of Outdoor Learning

Outdoor Learning has been shown to have many long-lasting benefits that include improved mental health,⁹ decreased stress levels,¹⁰ improved grades,¹¹ increased motivation,¹² positive attitudes towards the environment,¹³ better overall behaviour,¹⁴ increases in outdoor learning skills,¹⁵ improved memory,¹⁶ physical capabilities¹⁷ and learning about risk-taking.¹⁸

6 Active Healthy Kids Australia (2018). *Report Card 2018*. Retrieved 11/10/2020 from <https://www.activehealthykidsaustralia.com.au/siteassets/documents/2018/ahka-report-card-long-form-2018-final-for-web.pdf>

7 Copeland, K.A., Khoury, J.C., and Kalkwarf, H.J. (2016) 'Child care center characteristics associated with preschoolers' physical activity'. *American journal of preventive medicine*, 50(4), pp. 470–479.

8 Taylor, R.W., Murdoch, L., Carter, P., Gerrard, D.F., Williams, S.M., and Taylor, B.J. (2009) 'Longitudinal study of physical activity and inactivity in preschoolers: the FLAME study'. *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 41(1), pp. 96–102.

9 Nature Play QLD (2017). Benefits of going out and engaging with nature for kids. Retrieved 11/10/2020 from <https://natureplayqld.org.au/blog/15-benefits-of-going-out-and-engaging-with-nature-for-kids>

10 Dettweiler, U., Becker, C., Auestad, B.H., Simon, P., and Kirsch, P. (2017) 'Stress in school. Some empirical hints on the circadian cortisol rhythm of children in outdoor and indoor classes'. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 14(5), p. 475.

11 Dillon, J., Rickinson, M., Teamey, K., Morris, M., Choi, M.Y., Sanders, D., and Benefield, P. (2006) 'The value of outdoor learning: evidence from research in the UK and elsewhere'. *School science review*, 87(320), p. 107.

12 Bento, G., and Dias, G. (2017) The importance of outdoor play for young children's healthy development. *Porto Biomedical Journal*, 2(5), pp. 157–160.

13 Yerkes, R., and Haras, K. (1997) Outdoor Education and Environmental Responsibility. ERIC Digest.

14 Louv, R., and Charles, C. (2011) 'Battling the nature deficit with nature play'. *American Journal of Play*, 4(2).

15 Martin B., Cashel C., Wagstaff M., and Breunig M., (2007) *Outdoor Leadership: Theory and practice* (2nd edition) Champaign, IL, Human Kinetics, pp 305.

16 National Foundation for Educational Research in England and Wales, and Dillon, J. (2005). Engaging and learning with the outdoors: The final report of the outdoor classroom in a rural context action research project.

17 Coyle, K.J. (2010) Create High Performing Students.

18 Little, H., and Wyver, S. (2008) 'Outdoor play: Does avoiding the risks reduce the benefits?' *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, 33(2), pp. 33–40.

Launching an Outdoor Learning program

Depending on the type of Outdoor Learning program you wish to launch there are a range of considerations to factor into your planning. These include finding out what your school needs are, the environment, development of goals/criteria for success, the curriculum, staff training, how to create a safe, secure and inclusive environment, and the equipment needed for your specific programs. Once all these areas have been considered, you can move onto launching your Outdoor Learning program.

What does Outdoor Learning look like?

Outdoor Learning has close ties to its foundations in Outdoor Education, but its implementation is drastically different, Outdoor Learning does not require forests, lakes or rocks to climb and instead it harnesses the environment that is around you. Many of the best Outdoor Learning programs are conducted in schools on a playground, on the oval or in the garden. Activities that typically occur in a traditional classroom are often observed being taught on the playground, be that learning about mapping grids and alpha-numeric coordinates by having students use chalk, leaves, stones or feathers to create a grid on the playground instead of in a workbook.

Figure 3: Exploring the outdoors

Figure 4: Primary students understand the outdoors by exploring

Relationship back to Geography

In 2019, Outdoors Victoria worked with the Geography Teachers' Association of Victoria (GTAV) to investigate the connections between Geography and Outdoor Learning. By enabling primary students to engage in Geography learning in the outdoors, children can become comfortable and confident in their everyday geographies. The school grounds provide perfect environments for children to explore outside often – they are accessible and can stimulate student interest and motivation. By exploring further, students begin to develop understandings of places at different scales. Both provide excellent opportunities to embed curriculum outcomes in geographical ideas, concepts, content, geographical skills and geographical topics.

The topics that can broadly be included in the Geography curriculum include the:

- nature of places
- character of places
- sense of places
- management and improvement of places
- changing places
- place locations and connections
- comparing places.

Other resources on Outdoor Learning

Through the Strategic Partnership program, Outdoors Victoria, in partnership with the Australian Council for Health, Physical Education and Recreation (ACHPER Victoria), Environment Education Victoria (EEV), Geography Teachers Association (GTAV) and Parks Victoria (Parks Vic) are producing a series of 15 teacher toolkits. These unpack the benefits of Outdoor Learning, case studies of Outdoor Learning in Victorian primary schools, how to apply Outdoor Learning to specific learning areas, and specific environment types. In addition, these research-informed toolkits include sample letters home to families and tips on how to discuss Outdoor Learning with colleagues in addition to 150+ curriculum-aligned Outdoor Learning activities. More information on these toolkits can be found <https://outdoorsvictoria.org.au/outdoor-learning-toolkits/>

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